

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

This Certificate Awarded to :

Soatov Ulugbek Abdukadirovich

FOR PARTICIPATION AND PUBLICATION OF THE PAPER ENTITLED
ABOUT THE METHODS OF SOLVING GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS AT THE SCHOOL LEVEL

In A Multidisciplinary **"International Conference on Developments in Education"**,
Published with E-Conference Zone International Database, hosted online from Saint
Petersburg, Russia on November 24th, 2022.

www.econferencezone.org

Juliana Smith
RESEARCH DIRECTOR

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

This Certificate Awarded to :

**Djanizoqov Ulug'bek
Abdug'oniyevich**

FOR PARTICIPATION AND PUBLICATION OF THE PAPER ENTITLED
ABOUT THE METHODS OF SOLVING GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS AT THE SCHOOL LEVEL

In A Multidisciplinary **"International Conference on Developments in Education"**,
Published with E-Conference Zone International Database, hosted online from Saint
Petersburg, Russia on November 24th, 2022.

www.econferencezone.org

Juliana Smith
RESEARCH DIRECTOR

**ABOUT THE METHODS OF SOLVING GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS AT
THE SCHOOL LEVEL**

Soatov Ulugbek Abdukadirovich

Jizzax politexnika instituti dotsenti, f-m.f.n.
ulugbeksoatov595@gmail.com, tel: (94) 573 17 68

Djanizoqov Ulug'bek Abdug'oniyevich

Jizzax politexnika instituti katta o'qituvchisi
udjonuzoqov@gmail.com, tel: (93) 293 59 70.

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada turlicha qiyinchilikdagi ba'zi masalalarni yechish o'rganilgan bo'lib, ularni o'rganish va yechish orqali umumta'lim maktabi bitiruvchilarida geometrik masalalarni mustaqil yechish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish hamda geometrik masalalarni yechishda asosiy tushunchalar, teoremlar va formulalarni birgalikda qo'llashga doir turli usullar bilan tanishtirish maqsad qilingan.

Tayanch so'zlar: teorema, formula, bissektrisa, mediana, balandlik, diogonal, urunma, perpendikulyar, burchak, qavariq.

**ABOUT METHODS FOR SOLVING GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS AT
THE SCHOOL STAGE**

Soatov Ulugbek Abdukadirovich

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Associate Professor, Ph.D.
Soatov1966@mail.ru, tel: (94) 573 17 68

Dzhonizakov Ulugbek Abduganievich

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, senior lecturer
udjonuzoqov @ gmail.com, tel: (93) 293 59 70.

Annotation: this article explores the solution of some problems of varying severity, and through their study and solution, it is aimed to develop the skills of independent solution of geometric problems in graduates of Secondary School, as well as to familiarize themselves with various methods related to the joint application of basic concepts, theorems and formulas in solving geometric problems.

Keywords: theorem, formula, bisector, median, height, diagonal, urunma, perpendicular, angle, convex.

О МЕТОДАХ РЕШЕНИЯ ГЕОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ЗАДАЧ НА ШКОЛЬНОМ ЭТАПЕ

Соатов Улугбек Абдукадирович

Доцент Джизакского политехнического института, ф-м.ф.п.
ulugbeksoatov595@gmail.com, тел: (94) 573 17 68

Джанизоков Улугбек Абдугониевич

Ст.преподаватель Джизакского политехнического института
udjonuzoqov@gmail.com, тел: (93) 293 59 70.

Аннотация: В данной статье изучено решение некоторых задач с различной наклонностью, целью изучения и решения которых является формирование у выпускников общеобразовательных школ навыков самостоятельного решения геометрических задач, а также ознакомление с различными методами совместного применения основных понятий, теорем и формул при решении геометрических задач.

Ключевые слова: теорема, формула, биссектриса, медиана, высота, Диоген, умножение, перпендикуляр, угол, выпуклость.

Solving some geometric problems of varying difficulty requires the joint application of the basic theorems and formulas of geometry (planimetry). Engaging in the study and solution of this type of issue helps teachers, students and students to strengthen their knowledge, skills and abilities. Below we will study several geometric issues of this type.

Issue 1. Is that the square of the bisector of the angle of the Triangle is equal to the subtraction of the product of the cuts that we separate from the integer against the bisector by the product of the integers attached to it, i.e.

$l^2 = ab - a_1b_1$ prove equality.

Solution: we look at the triangles ACD and BCD (fig. 1):

1) according to the cosine theorem $b_1^2 = b^2 + l_c^2 - 2bl_c \cos \alpha$,

$a_1^2 = a^2 + l_c^2 - 2al_c \cos \alpha$, in this $\alpha = \frac{\angle C}{2}$ From this

$$\frac{2bl_c \cos \alpha}{2al_c \cos \alpha} = \frac{b^2 + l_c^2 - b_1^2}{a^2 + l_c^2 - a_1^2}, \text{ that is}$$

$$l_c^2(b - a) = ab(b - a) - (ab_1^2 - a_1^2b)$$

(A)

2) According to the property of the bisector of the Triangle $\frac{a}{b} = \frac{a_1}{b_1}$ that is

$$ab_1 = ba_1.$$

Without it

$$ab_1^2 - a_1^2b = a_1bb_1 - a_1b_1a = a_1b_1(b - a) \text{ and (a)}$$

equality

$$l_c^2(b - a) = ab(b - a) - a_1b_1(b - a) \text{ comes to view or}$$

if $b \neq a$ if, $l_c^2 = ab - a_1b_1$. If $a = b$, then

$$b_1 = a_1 = \frac{c}{2}, \quad b_1^2 = a^2 - \frac{c^2}{4} \quad \text{and} \quad l_c^2 = a^2 - \frac{c^2}{4}.$$

Say, $l^2 = ab - a_1b_1$ appropriate.

Issue 2. Two circles intersect at a right angle (that is, their attempts through one of the points of intersection are mutually perpendicular). If the radii of the circles are R and r, Find the cross section (length) of the total attempt of these circles.

Solution: O_1 and O_2 are given centers of circles, M-one of their intersection points, AB - let it be a common attempt (fig.2)

From the intersection of circles at a right angle, it follows that O_1M is perpendicular to O_2M .

$$\text{Therefore } O_1O_2 = \sqrt{R^2 + r^2}$$

Let $R > r$. We pass BC parallel to O_1O_2 and look at ΔABC ($\angle A = 90^\circ$). According to the Pythagorean theorem

$$AB = \sqrt{BC^2 - AC^2} = \sqrt{R^2 + r^2 - (R - r)^2} = \sqrt{2Rr}.$$

If $R = r$, then

$$AB = O_1O_2 = R\sqrt{2}. \text{ So, } AB = \sqrt{2Rr}.$$

Issue 3. The sides of a triangle are 25, 24, and 7.

Determine the faces of the circles drawn inside and outside it.

fig.1

fig.2

fig.3

Solution: It is convenient to solve the problem in the following order:

- 1) Let's mark the sides of the triangle with a, b, c.
 Suppose $a=7, b=24, c=25$.
- 2) We determine the type of $\triangle ABC$: $a^2+b^2=625$ and $c^2=625$, that is, since $a^2+b^2=c^2$, according to the reverse theorem of the Pythagorean theorem, $\triangle ABC$ is right-angled (fig. 3).
- 3) The center of the circle drawn outside the triangle is O_1 - at the point of intersection of the middle perpendiculars transferred to the sides of the triangle. In a right-angled triangle, the center of the inscribed circle is the center of the hypotenuse, that is, $R=\frac{c}{2}=12,5$.
- 4) The center O of the circle inscribed in the triangle is at the point where the bisectors of the triangle intersect.
- 5) $BD=BF=x, AE=AF=y$, according to the property of cross-sections of attempts made from a point outside the circle.
- 6). $BC=a=7$ or $r+x=7$ according to the condition. $AC=b=24$ or $r+y=24$ by adding these equalities $2r+(x+y)=31$ or $2r+AB=31, 2r+25=31$. From this $r=3$.
- 7). Let S_1 -inscribed and S_2 -external be the faces of circles.

Then $S_1 = \pi r^2 = 9\pi$ (sq. unit.) $S_2 = \pi R^2 = 12,5^2 \pi = \frac{625}{4} \pi$ (sq. unit.).

Note: R and r radii can be found using the formulas $R = \frac{abc}{2ab} = \frac{c}{2} = 12,5$ and

$$S_{\triangle ABC} = pr : R = \frac{abc}{2ab} = \frac{c}{2} = 12,5, r = \frac{S}{a+b+c} = \frac{168}{56} = 3.$$

Issue 4. A triangle ABC with face equal to 1 is given. (figure 4). The medians of the triangle are AK, BL and CN , respectively, and points Q and R are taken

$$\frac{AP}{PK} = 1, \frac{BQ}{QL} = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{CR}{RN} = \frac{5}{4}. \text{ Find the face of triangle } PQR.$$

Solution: Let the point O be the point of intersection of the medians of the triangle ABC . In that case

$$S_{\triangle AOB} = S_{\triangle BOC} = S_{\triangle AOC} = S_{\triangle ABC} = \frac{1}{3}$$

Let's look at the triangle $\triangle POQ$. In this

$$OP = \frac{2}{3}AK - \frac{1}{2}AK = \frac{1}{6}AK$$

fig.4

$$OQ = \frac{2}{3}BL - \frac{1}{3}BL = \frac{1}{3}BL. \quad \text{And} \quad S_{\Delta POQ} = \frac{1}{2}OP \cdot OQ \sin \angle POQ,$$

$$S_{\Delta AOB} = \frac{1}{2}OA \cdot OB \sin \angle AOB, \quad \text{if it is taken into account that}$$

$$\frac{S_{\Delta POQ}}{S_{\Delta AOB}} = \frac{OP \cdot OQ}{OA \cdot OB} = \frac{\frac{1}{6}AK \cdot \frac{1}{3}BL}{\frac{2}{3}AK \cdot \frac{2}{3}BL} = \frac{1}{8}. \text{ From this } S_{\Delta OPQ} = \frac{1}{8}S_{\Delta AOB} \text{ we will have.}$$

$$\text{Similarly, we have } S_{\Delta OPQ} = \frac{1}{12}S_{\Delta BOC}, \quad S_{\Delta POR} = \frac{1}{24}S_{\Delta AOC}$$

$$\text{Therefore } S_{\Delta PQR} = \frac{1}{3}\left(\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{24}\right) = \frac{1}{12} \text{ (sq. unit).}$$

Issue 5. Find the ratio of the radii of the inner and outer circles of an equilateral triangle with the base α -acute angle.

Solution: ΔABC is an equilateral triangle.

Let $\angle A = \angle C = \alpha$. (fig. 5). We can define $AC=b$. According to the theorem of

sines $\frac{b}{\sin \alpha} = R$. Here, R is the radius of the outer

circle. Since the angles at the base of the triangle are equal to α ,

$$\angle B = 180^\circ - 2\alpha \quad \text{and}$$

$$\sin B = \sin(180^\circ - \alpha) = \sin 2\alpha. \quad \text{So,}$$

$$R = \frac{b}{\sin \alpha}.$$

Now let point O be the center of the inscribed

circle. Then $\angle OAD = \frac{\alpha}{2}$. that is why

$$r = OD = AD \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2} = \frac{b}{2} \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2}. \quad \text{From this}$$

$$\frac{r}{R} = \sin 2\alpha \operatorname{tg} \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

fig.5

Issue 6. The sides of triangle ABC are equal to a, b, c . Find its m_a, m_b, m_c - medians (figure 6).

Solution: Method 1. $m_b = BB_1$ to find the median, we continue it to the B_1D -section equal to BB_1 and connect point D with points A and C . The resulting quadrilateral $ABCD$ is a parallelogram because the diagonals AC and BD are

bisected at the point of intersection. The sum of the squares of the diagonals of a parallelogram is equal to the sum of the squares of its sides, i.e.

$$b^2 + (2m_b)^2 = 2a^2 + 2c^2. \quad \text{From this}$$

$$m_b = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2a^2 + 2c^2 - b^2}.$$

Similarly, the medians m_a and m_c are found.

Method 2. Let $\angle AB_1B = \alpha$. Then $\angle BB_1C = 180^\circ - \alpha$. According to the theorem of cosines

$$c^2 = \frac{b^2}{4} + m_b^2 - 2m_b \frac{b}{2} \cos \alpha,$$

$$a^2 = \frac{b^2}{4} + m_b^2 - 2m_b \frac{b}{2} \cos(180^\circ - \alpha)$$

Adding these equations,

$$\text{Considering that } \cos(180^\circ - \alpha) = -\cos \alpha,$$

$$a^2 + c^2 = \frac{b^2}{2} + 2m_b^2. \quad \text{From this } m_b = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2a^2 + 2c^2 - b^2}.$$

In conclusion, we can say that it is not difficult to understand that the study of geometric problems with a high degree of complexity, including the solution of the geometric problems presented in this article, lies in the expansion of the basic methods and substitution formulas. In this process, it is important to correctly imagine the shape of the geometric figure (shape) given in the problem and reflect it in the drawing and to be able to use its properties correctly, and by strengthening the acquired knowledge, one or the other the ability to solve problems develops. There are also many complex problems related to other topics of geometry[1-16], regularly continuing to solve them for a certain period of time helps to develop mathematical ability.

References

1. Sh.A.Alimov, Yu.M.Kolyagin va boshqalar. Algebra va analiz asoslari. O'rta maktab-ning 10- 11- sinf uchun darslik. -T.: O'qituvchi, 2001.
2. В.С.Крамор. «Павторяем и систематизируем школьный курс алгебры и начал анализа», Москва, «Просвещение», 1990

3. И.Ф.Шарыгин, В.И. Голубев. Факультативный курс по математике решение задач. Москва, «Просвещение». 1991 .
4. Soatov, U. A. (2018). Djonuzoqov. UA" Problems of geometry with the help of joint application of basic theorems and formulas". *Scientific-methodical journal of" Physics, Mathematics and Informatics"*, (4), 40.
5. Soatov Ulugbek Abdukadirovich, & Dzhonuzokov Ulugbek Abduganievich (2020). ABOUT THE ISSUES OF GEOMETRICAL INEQUALITIES AND THE METHODS OF THEIR SOLUTION. *European science*, (7 (56)), 5-10.
6. Abdukadirovich, S. U., & Abduganievich, D. U. (2021, June). ON SOME PROBLEMS OF EXTREME PROPERTIES OF THE FUNCTION AND THE APPLICATION OF THE DERIVATIVE AND METHODS FOR THEIR SOLUTION. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 113-117).
7. Abdug'aniyevich, D. U. B. (2022). PARAMETRLI LOGARIFMIK TENGLAMALARNI YECHISH USULLARIGA OID BA'ZI MASALALAR. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 5(1), 8-16.
8. Соатов, У. А. Сложные события и расчет их вероятностей / У. А. Соатов, У. А. Джанизоков // Экономика и социум. – 2022. – № 1-2(92). – С. 222-227.
9. Abdukadirovich, S. U., & Abduganievich, D. U. (2022). ABOUT THE METHODS OF SOLVING PARAMETRIC EQUATIONS. *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 1(5), 1-7.
10. Soatov U.A. U.A. Djonuzoqov."Irratsional tenglama va tengsizliklarni yechish metodlarining tatbiqlari haqida".*Scientific-methodical journal of" Physics, Mathematics and Informatics"*. 2019. № 4. 8-16.
11. Soatov U.A. U.A. Djonuzoqov."Tenglamalar sistemalarini tuzish va ularni yechishga oid ba'zi masalalar haqida".*Scientific-methodical journal of" Physics, Mathematics and Informatics"*. 2019. № 1.13-20.
12. Гадаев, Р. Р. О семействе обобщенных моделей Фридрикса / Р. Р. Гадаев, У. А. Джанизоков // Молодой ученый. – 2016. – № 13(117). – С. 5-7.
13. Гадаев, Р. Р., Джанизоков, У. А., & Ахадова, К. С. К. (2020). ОПРЕДЕЛИТЕЛЬ ФРЕДГОЛЬМА ДВУМЕРНОЙ ОБОБЩЕННОЙ МОДЕЛИ ФРИДРИХСА. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (12 (59)).
14. Бердиев, А. Ш. Построение периодических решений с помощью метода Простых итераций / А. Ш. Бердиев, У. А. Джанизоков, У. У. Арслонов // Экономика и социум. – 2021. – № 12-1(91). – С. 858-864.

15. Soatov, U. A. (2022). Logarfmik funksiya qatnashgan murakkab tenglamalarni yechish usullari haqida. *Science and Education*, 3(9), 16-22.
16. Soatov, U. A. (2022). Tenglamalarni yechishning grafik usuli haqida. *Science and Education*, 3(8), 7-12